

Enhanced Photothermal Conversion through 2D/0D Nano-Heterojunction Engineering for Highly Efficient Solar Desalination

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Abstract

Two-dimensional (2D) materials are promising candidates for solar-driven desalination. Conventional photothermal materials such as transition metal carbides and nitrides (MXenes) or transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) suffer from major limitations due to complex synthesis and low photothermal conversion efficiency. Conversely, metal phosphorus trichalcogenides (MPCh₃) do not display the same drawbacks and also possess widely tunable bandgaps (1.3–3.5 eV), making them ideal components for desalination using solar energy. Moreover, the light-matter interaction related properties and applications can potentially be further enhanced upon interfacing them to other low-dimensional nanostructures by tailoring hybrid van der Waals heterostructures of mixed dimensionality. Herein, we synthesized FePS₃ nanosheets/carbon nanodots (CNDs) 2D/0D nano-heterojunctions and tested their photothermal response when integrated in a 3D photothermal evaporator. The nano-heterojunctions exhibit extremely high photothermal conversion performance, with an average absorbance of 90.6% from the visible to the NIR, a temperature increase of 42 °C superior to the blank control under 1 sun illumination for 300 s is found. A high water evaporation rate of 1.68 kg m⁻² h⁻¹ is seen under the same illumination condition.

Photothermal conversion and water evaporation experiments, along with femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy (fs-TAS) and photoluminescence (PL) analysis corroborated by finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) simulations, demonstrate that the incorporation of CNDs and the formation of the nano-heterojunction synergistically enhance localized heating, improve light absorption and trapping efficiency, and optimize non-radiative transition pathways. This study highlights the enhanced photothermal performance achieved through MPCh₃-based nano-heterojunction engineering, revealing its disruptive potential to advance 2D materials for solar desalination and photothermal applications.

Introduction

Photothermal conversion, directly converting solar energy into heat, has emerged as an effective strategy for solar desalination, thermoelectric devices, cancer therapy, etc.^[1–3] By leveraging photothermal materials with high solar absorption and efficient photothermal conversion, solar-driven desalination enables the production of clean water from seawater, offering a promising solution to global water scarcity.^[4,5] Two-dimensional (2D) materials, such as transition metal carbides and nitrides (MXenes), black phosphorus (BP), and graphene etc., have received increasing attention as photothermal materials.^[6] However, their complex synthesis, poor stability, and limited photothermal conversion efficiency hinder their further application.^[7–9] Consequently, the development of novel 2D photothermal materials has emerged as a key focus of ongoing research.

Metal phosphorus trichalcogenides (MPCh₃), where M represents metal (such as Fe, Ni, Mn, Co, etc.) and Ch represents S or Se,^[13] have garnered significant interest due to their layered structure, widely tunable bandgap (1.33.5 eV), and strong light absorption in the visible (vis) and near-infrared regions (NIR).^[10–12] The diverse metal compositions endow MPCh₃ materials with plasmonic effects and broad solar absorption, making them

promising candidates for photothermal conversion.^[14] As a representative MPCh₃ material, NiPS₃ nanosheets have been explored for the first time in photothermal conversion and seawater desalination.^[15] However, the research on MPCh₃ materials has mostly focused on pristine MPCh₃ nanosheets, leaving the functionalization of MPCh₃-based materials largely underexplored, severely hindering their potential in photothermal conversion.

Currently, several strategies have been employed to improve the photothermal conversion efficiency of 2D materials. For example, the interfacing with 0D noble metal nanoparticles (e.g. Au, Ag) can enhance the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) effect, thereby improving light absorption and photothermal conversion.^[16] However, this approach is prone to aggregation, which can negatively affect the physical properties of the hybrid.^[17] Structural modulation, by increasing the materials porosity, is a viable strategy to improve light capture and reduce light reflection, thereby enhancing photothermal conversion efficiency.^[18] Nevertheless, the fabrication of these structures is often time consuming, costly and lacks high precision.^[19] Surface molecular functionalization primarily enables to adjust the hydrophilicity or hydrophobicity of the material, yielding a reduction of the thermal losses or promotion of water transport, though excessive modification may compromise material

stability or alter the behavior of water molecules at the interface.^[6,20]

Therefore, designing low-cost, efficient, and scalable strategies based on the molecular functionalization of novel 2D materials to further improve photothermal conversion performance and water evaporation rates can lead to significant advancement in solar desalination.

Here, we synthesized FePS₃ nanosheets/carbon nanodots (CNDs) 2D/0D nano-heterojunctions and exploited them as active components in the fabrication of a three-dimensional (3D) evaporator, enabling efficient photothermal conversion and solar desalination. Compared with the pristine FePS₃ nanosheets and CNDs, the nano-heterojunction-based evaporators exhibit significantly enhanced photothermal conversion temperature and water evaporation rate. Under 1 sun illumination, the water evaporation rate exceeds 1.68 kg m⁻² h⁻¹ and increases with CNDs loading, thereby surpassing the theoretical limit of photothermal conversion efficiency (1.47 kg m⁻² h⁻¹ at 1 kW m⁻²).^[21] A combination of absorbance spectroscopy, finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) simulations, femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy (fs-TAS), and photoluminescence (PL) analysis reveals that, compared to pristine FePS₃ nanosheets and CNDs, the hybridization determines significantly enhanced local heating, improved light

absorption and trapping capabilities, and optimized non-radiative transition pathways. This study not only introduces a new protocol to form multifunctional MPC_{h3}-based nano-heterojunctions, but also offers a new powerful route for enhanced photothermal conversion by promoting MPC_{h3} materials as a prototypical component. More generally, these findings contribute to the advancement of 2D materials and the development of high-performance photothermal conversion devices.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1. The preparation scheme of FePS₃/CNDs 2D/0D nano-heterojunctions for solar desalination.

The FePS₃/CNDs 2D/0D nano-heterojunctions were assembled as 3D evaporators for photothermal conversion and solar desalination following the procedure portrayed in **Figure 1**. FePS₃ crystals synthesized via chemical vapor transport (CVT) were exfoliated by means of wet grinding exfoliation (WGE),^[22] yielding a nanosheet dispersion in a solvent mixture (1:1 v/v water/isopropanol (IPA)). 10 mL of this FePS₃ nanosheet dispersion was then mixed with

different volumes of CNDs dispersion (1 mg/mL) synthesized via the hydrothermal method to obtain FePS₃/CNDs 2D/0D nano-heterojunctions dispersion. These dispersions have been deposited onto the surface of 3D sponge which acts as water transportation channel for water and its vapors as well as supporting material. To enhance the adhesion of the dispersions onto the sponge surface and decrease the propensity of FePS₃ nanosheets to undergo oxidation and aggregation, the mixed dispersion was further combined with 1 mL of 5 wt.% polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) aqueous solution to form a stable composite dispersion. PVA was chosen since it has been demonstrated that it does not affect the photothermal conversion performance.^[15] The three components of nano-heterojunction dispersions were prepared by mixing FePS₃ nanosheet dispersion and CNDs dispersion at 10:1 (v/v), 10:2 (v/v), and 10:4 (v/v), followed by the addition of 1 mL of PVA aqueous solution to each mixture, yielding FeC1, FeC2, and FeC4, respectively. Finally, 2 mL of the prepared FeC1, FeC2, and FeC4 dispersions were uniformly drop-cast onto the sponges and dried at 110 °C to obtain FeC1@S, FeC2@S, and FeC4@S, respectively. The process was repeated 6–8 times until the dispersions were entirely adsorbed onto the sponge's surface, yielding the 3D evaporators for photothermal conversion and solar desalination.

Figure 2. Characterizations of the pristine FePS₃ and CNDs. a) SEM image of FePS₃ bulk crystals. AFM height image of b) exfoliated FePS₃ nanosheets and c) corresponding topographical profiles. d) Atomically resolved HAADF-STEM images, and e) corresponding STEM-EELS maps. f) XRD patterns of bulk FePS₃ and FePS₃ nanosheets on the glass substrate. g) Overview HAADF-STEM image and corresponding STEM-EELS maps of FePS₃ nanosheets. h) TEM images of CNDs. i) Normalized absorption spectra of FePS₃ nanosheets and CNDs.

Figure 2 shows the characterization of pristine FePS₃ and CNDs. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image in **Figure 2a** reveals that the FePS₃ crystal before exfoliation displays its characteristic layered structure. **Figures 2b** and **c** show the atomic force microscopy (AFM) height image of FePS₃ nanosheets and

corresponding topographical profiles, revealing a thickness of approximately 7–15 nm, which corresponds to around 10–20 layers.^[23] To gain in-depth insight into crystallinity and atomic structure of FePS₃ nanosheets, high-angle annular dark-field STEM (HAADF-STEM) analysis was performed, as shown in **Figures 2d** and **e**. The colored HAADF-STEM image in **Figure 2d** reveals a rotational twin structure in FePS₃ along the (1 0 3) crystal plane, with distinct lattice spacing of 0.17 nm, which is consistent with literature reports.^[24] It further demonstrates that the exfoliated nanosheets retain excellent crystalline structure. Additionally, atomic-resolution electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) mapping was obtained for the layered FePS₃ nanosheets, revealing the atomic-scale distribution of different elements.

The crystal structure of FePS₃ was analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) in the 2θ range from 10° to 80°. As evidenced in **Figure 2f**, bulk FePS₃ crystals adopt a monoclinic structure with the space group *C2/m*.^[25] Compared to bulk FePS₃ crystals, the FePS₃ nanosheets exhibit decreased peak intensity and broadened diffraction peaks, indicating the successful exfoliation of 2D structures. The composition of FePS₃ nanosheets was further investigated using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). In **Figure S1** (Supporting Information), the high-resolution XPS spectra

of FePS₃ nanosheets display well-defined peaks for Fe 2p, P 2p, and S 2p, confirming the chemical composition of exfoliated FePS₃.^[26] Additionally, the Raman spectrum of FePS₃ nanosheets (Figure S2, Supporting Information) was acquired using a 532 nm excitation laser. Raman peaks in the range of 50–600 cm⁻¹ originate from the A_{1g} and E_g vibrational modes of the P₂S₆ unit, aligning well with previously reported literature.^[27] The EELS mapping in **Figure 2g** further confirms the uniform distribution of Fe, P, and S elements across the nanosheet (corresponding EELS spectra are provided in Figure S3). The transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image of CNDs in **Figure 2h** shows that the CNDs have an average size of approximately 10 nm. Absorption spectra recorded on both FePS₃ nanosheets and CNDs exhibit a gradual decrease in absorbance with increasing wavelength (**Figure 2i**), with a characteristic absorption peak observed at approximately 335 nm for the CNDs, in line with previously reported results.^[26,28]

Figure 3. Characterizations of the FePS₃/CNDs hybrid materials. a) TEM images of FePS₃/CNDs nano-heterojunctions (volume ratio is 10:1). b) AFM images of FeC1. c) Normalized absorption spectra of FeC1 (the inset depicts the corresponding dispersion). 2D PL mapping of d) FePS₃ nanosheets, e) CNDs, and f) FeC1. Water contact angle measurements of g) blank Si wafer, h) FePS₃ nanosheets and i) FePS₃/CNDs hybrid materials onto Si wafer.

The FePS₃/CNDs hybrid materials, obtained by mixing the as-prepared FePS₃ nanosheets and CNDs, were characterized using TEM, AFM, UV-vis absorption and photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopies as well as contact angle measurements. The corresponding results are presented in **Figure 3**. The TEM image in **Figure 3a** reveals the presence of large-area, transparent FePS₃ nanosheets with well-defined edges. The red arrows indicate

uniformly distributed, small-sized nanoparticles on the surface of the FePS₃ nanosheets, which are consistent with the morphology of CNDs. This observation confirms the successful loading of CNDs onto the FePS₃ nanosheets, resulting in the formation of 2D/0D nano-heterostructures. AFM image in **Figure 3b** displays the morphology of the nano-heterojunction obtained upon mixing the FePS₃/CNDs 2D/0D nano-heterojunction with PVA, yielding the FeCx hybrids. In that specific case, the FeC1 thin films show a polymeric network of PVA (blue arrow) with a thickness of ca. 10-15 nm, which is sporadically coated with the FePS₃/CNDs hybrid (red arrow) determining a further increase in thickness of ca. 15 nm (see Figure S4 for topographical profile). The results show that the nano-heterojunctions preferentially physisorb onto the PVA network.

The photophysical properties of FeC1 dispersions in IPA/water were investigated via steady-state absorption and emission spectroscopy. The FeC1 dispersions exhibit broad, structureless absorption spanning across UV, vis, and NIR regions, resembling those observed for FePS₃ nanosheets (**Figure 3c**). The higher absorbance of FePS₃ compared to CNDs likely results in the masking of the CND absorption features by FePS₃. Subsequently, the emission spectra of FeC1 dispersions at different wavelengths of photoexcitation were compared to that of FePS₃ and CNDs

(**Figure 3d-f**). As shown in **Figures 3e** and **S5a**, CNDs in IPA/water exhibit excitation-dependent emission, with two strong emissions at 400-500 nm and 500-600 nm, respectively. Taking a closer look, CNDs display excitation-independent emission with a maximum of around 455 nm under photoexcitation in the region of 250-380 nm. When the photoexcitation wavelength exceeds 400 nm, an excitation-dependent emission was observed. In other words, the emission in the 500-600 nm range exhibited a red-shifted emission with longer wavelengths of photoexcitation. In contrast, no appreciable emission is observed for FePS₃ in IPA/water (**Figure 3d**). Interestingly, the emission spectra of FeC1 exhibited a dramatically different picture (**Figure 3f** and **S5b**). Upon photoexcitation with a wavelength exceeding 390 nm, the emission of FeC1 exhibits similar properties to that seen for CNDs, thus possessing excitation-dependent emission in the 500–600 nm range. Note that the emission intensity of FeC1 in this spectral range is comparable to the Raman peaks of solvents and much weaker than that observed in CNDs. In addition, at photoexcitation wavelengths below 390 nm, emission from CNDs is completely quenched. These observations confirm that the formation of nano-heterojunction between CNDs and FePS₃ nanosheets. Moreover, the quantitative quenching of CND emission in FeC1 suggests that non-radiative

deactivation due to heterojunction formation, such as thermal transition, dominates after light absorbance of FeC1.

Next, the hydrophobicity of films of FePS₃ nanosheets and FePS₃/CNDs nano-heterojunctions onto Si wafers were investigated by means of contact angle measurements. **Figures 3g** and **h** reveal that FePS₃ nanosheets possess a greater hydrophobicity compared to just the Si wafer. Upon addition of CNDs, the contact angle significantly decreases, indicating an enhancement in hydrophilicity (**Figure 3i**). This change is attributed to the presence of -COOH, -NH₂, and -OH termini on the CNDs surface. These findings suggest that the FePS₃/CNDs hybrid materials are favorable for water evaporation.

To gain insight into the light energy conversion process in FeC1, the excited state dynamics of FeC1 in IPA/water were measured and compared with FePS₃ nanosheets using fs-TAS upon 390 nm photoexcitation (**Figure 4a–d**). Immediately after the photoexcitation of FePS₃ nanosheets in IPA/water, a broad positive signal in the 400-700 nm range centered at around 450 nm was observed and assigned to an excited stated absorption (ESA) (**Figure 4a** and **S6a**). Notably, when delay times reached around 1 ns, the ESA disappeared completely, suggesting that no additional excited states were involved in this physical process. Moreover, one species

with a lifetime of around 250 ps is suitable for fitting the fs-TAS data through global analysis (**Figure 4b** and S7a). FeC1 in IPA/water shows similar excited state dynamics as that summarized for FePS₃ nanosheets (**Figures 4c** and d; Figure S6b and S7b). Following photoexcitation of 390 nm, a broad ESA was discernable. Here, the maximum is observed at around 450 nm, which correlates with a hypsochromatic shift compared to that observed for FePS₃ nanosheets. A newly formed excited state across the nano-heterojunction with a lower energy gap is considered responsible for the underlying hypsochromatic shift. Moreover, the fs-TAS of FeC1 is best fitted by a single species with a lifetime of around 260 ps. Our results indicate that this new excited state, due to the nano-heterojunction formation, is populated immediately after photoexcitation or with a rate that is covered by the resolution of fs-TAS and subsequently relaxes directly to the ground state. Considering that FeC1 is non-emissive under photoexcitation 390 nm and beyond (vide supra), we consider that the excitons undergo non-radiative decay and release heat.

Figure 4. fs-TAS and FDTD simulation of FePS₃/CNDs. Heat map of femtosecond transient absorption (fs-TAS) raw data of a) FePS₃ and c) FeC1 obtained in pump-probe experiments after photoexcitation at 390 nm. Evolution-associated spectra (EAS) of the deconvoluted species for b) FePS₃ and d) FeC1. Inset: Time absorption profiles and corresponding fits of selected wavelengths. Electric field enhancement (EFE) of e) single FePS₃ nanosheets and f) FeC1 at a broadband range from UV light (300 nm) to NIR light (2000 nm).

To further explain the excellent optical absorption properties of 2D/0D FeC_x nano-heterojunctions, we constructed a simplified model for the FDTD simulation. In our comparative assessment, we focus on four different wavelengths, namely 350, 500, 1206, and 2000 nm to cover the entire solar spectrum, that is, from the UV all the way to the NIR. **Figures 4e, f,** and S8 show the FDTD simulation

model of the FePS₃ nanosheets and FeCx (FeC1, FeC2, and FeC4) structures. In this model, compared to pristine FePS₃ nanosheets, CNDs in FeCx nanostructures are uniformly distributed across the surfaces of the FePS₃ nanosheets and progressively increase in quantity (Figure S9, Supporting Information). For FeC4, the strongest electric field distribution is seen at each wavelength. According to previous work,^[29] for FeCx, the absorption ability (P_{abs}) of electromagnetic power corresponds to:

$$P_{abs} = \frac{1}{2} \omega \cdot \text{Im}(\varepsilon) \cdot |E|^2 \quad (1)$$

where ω is the angular frequency of incident light, $\text{Im}(\varepsilon)$ belongs to the imaginary part of the permittivity of FeC4, and $|E|$ stands for the amplitude of the total electric field intensity. In our FeCx samples, ω is $2\pi c/\lambda$ and $\text{Im}(\varepsilon)$ is a constant. Thus, $|E|^2$ determines the absorption capacity at a specific wavelength. With increasing wavelength, the absorption capacity gradually increases, in general, and at the interfaces with CNDs, in particular. In turn, it highlights the solar spectrum absorption performance of the FeCx samples. It suggests that introducing CNDs enhances light absorption and thermal localization. Both are inferred from the electric field distribution corresponding to multiple absorption wavelengths.^[30,31]

Figure 5. Characterizations and performance of FePS₃/CNDs-based evaporators. (a) Photograph of the blank sponge (left) and impregnated with FeC1@S (right). (b) Optical microscope image of the blank sponge. (c, d) SEM images of FeC1@S with increasing magnification. (e) Absorbance of the blank@S, FeC1@S, FePS₃@S, and CNDs@S from wavelength 300 to 2500 nm. (f) The surface temperature of blank@S, FeC1@S, FeC2@S, FeC4@S, FePS₃@S, and CNDs-S changes with time when the Xe lamp is turned on or off under an optical density of 1 kW m⁻² (1 sun). (g) The real-time surface temperatures of the blank-S and FeC1@S are monitored by an IR camera under 1 sun irradiation for 300 s. (h) Schematic diagram of solar water evaporation. (i) Surface temperature change during photothermal water evaporation for the blank-S and FeC1@S. (j) Photothermal conversion evaporation rate under different conditions. (k) Mass change during photothermal water evaporation for blank-S and FeC1@S under 1 sun irradiation. (l) Cyclic water evaporation test of FeC1@S under 1 sun irradiation. (m) Evaporation rates of different sized evaporators under 1 sun irradiation. (n) Measured concentration of Na⁺, Mg²⁺, and Ca²⁺ before and after solar desalination.

To validate our FDTD simulations, fs-TAS, and PL analysis, and to demonstrate the effectiveness of the designed nano-heterojunctions in photothermal conversion, we fabricated FeC_x@S, FePS₃@S, and CNDs@S 3D evaporators and systematically evaluated their photothermal conversion and water evaporation performance. **Figure 5a** portrays the blank sponge (blank@S) and the FeC₁@S evaporator, both with dimensions of 2 × 2 × 0.5 cm³. Compared to blank@S, the impregnated sponge color changed from yellow to black, indicating its strong potential for photothermal conversion. As shown in Figure S10 (Supporting Information), in view of the evaporator's limited weight determined by its high porosity and low density, it can be supported on a dandelion without observing a noticeable deformation.

The intrinsic hydrophilicity of PVA imparts excellent wettability to the FeC₁@S evaporator, as evidenced by the rapid absorption of a water droplet within 1 s during the contact angle measurements (Figure S11, Supporting Information). Optical microscopy (OM) and SEM were also employed to examine the FeC₁@S 3D evaporator (**Figures 5b–d**). OM and SEM images (**Figures 5b** and **c**) reveal that the sponge features pore sizes below 100 μm, which facilitates efficient water transport, vapor escape, and salt diffusion during the water evaporation. As shown in **Figure 5d**, the

FePS₃/CNDs 2D/0D nano-heterojunctions are well-coated on the sponge surface. This is instrumental to guarantee an efficient photothermal conversion and solar-driven desalination.^[32] PVA facilitates their adhesion onto the sponge and prevents their oxidation. Both of them are beneficial for solar desalination.

Prior to evaluating the water evaporation performance, we measured the light absorption of the fabricated 3D evaporators across the UV-vis-NIR region, namely from 250 to 2500 nm. As shown in **Figures 5e** and S12 (Supporting Information), FeC1@S exhibits a significantly higher average light absorption (90.6%) compared to blank@S (42.8%), FePS₃-loaded sponge (FePS₃@S, 84.9%), and CNDs-loaded sponge (CNDs@S, 85.6%). This is consistent with the FDTD simulations and confirms that the nano-heterojunction structure enhances light absorption.

The photothermal conversion of the evaporator was further studied by monitoring the temperature rise under 1 sun irradiation in air (**Figures 5f** and **g**). The dry FeC1@S evaporator exhibited a rapid temperature increase from 23.6 °C to 48.6 °C within 1 min, reaching 61.7 °C after 300 s. This is higher than the peak temperatures recorded for blank@S (33.0 °C), FePS₃@S (58.3 °C), and CNDs@S (59.9 °C) under the same conditions and underlines its superior photothermal conversion. To further assess the impact

of CNDS loading on photothermal performance, we conducted the same tests with FeC2@S and FeC4@S. After 300 s, their surface temperatures reached 65.1 °C and 64.7 °C, respectively. Higher CNL loadings is linked to higher photothermal conversions. A maximum temperature difference of roundabout 42 °C, highlights the excellent localized heating effect enabled by the nano-heterojunction.

Figure 5h portrays the scheme of the water evaporation setup. As water is rapidly transported through the microchannels to the evaporator surface, a continuous water supply during solar evaporation is secured. All evaporation experiments with the FeCx@S evaporators were performed at ≈ 22 °C and $\approx 36\%$ RH. Figure S13 displays the infrared images of FeC1@S and the blank@S and highlights not only the rapid photothermal response, but also the distinct equilibrium temperatures under 1 kW m^{-2} illumination. Surface temperature changes that correspond the findings made with FeC1@S and blank@S are shown in **Figure 5i**. Hereby, the surface temperature increases rapidly and is stabilized within 20 min. After 50 min, the temperature of FeC1@S (38 °C) is higher than that of blank@S and an equilibrium temperature difference of ≈ 7 °C is observed between FeC1@S and blank@S.

The evaporation rate was evaluated by measuring the mass loss

of water, which was recorded using an analytical balance at the start ($t = 0$ min) and end ($t = 60$ min) of the evaporation. The evaporation rate (r) was calculated using the following equation:^[33]

$$r = \frac{\Delta m}{ST} \quad (2)$$

where Δm represents the mass difference, S the surface area of the solar evaporator, and T the evaporation time. The evaporation rates of pure water, blank@S, FePS₃@S, CNDs@S, and FeCx@S are summarized in **Figure 5j**. Compared to pure water and blank@S, FeCx@S evaporators exhibited significantly higher evaporation rates. An evaporation rate of 1.68–1.72 kg m⁻² h⁻¹ under 1 sun irradiation exceeds the theoretical photothermal evaporation limit of 1.47 kg m⁻² h⁻¹. The nano-heterojunction-based evaporator demonstrated also excellent stability in solar-driven seawater evaporation. Next, we monitored the mass change of both the blank@S and FeC1@S under 1 sun irradiation over time (**Figure 5k**). Within 60 min, the mass change in FeC1@S is greater than that seen in blank@S. The stability of the evaporator was further evaluated and is presented in **Figure 5l**. FeC1@S maintained an average water evaporation rate of 1.681 kg m⁻² h⁻¹ over 9 cycles.

To investigate the effect of 3D evaporator size on the evaporation performance, FeC1@S evaporators were fabricated with square surfaces having side lengths of 2, 3, and 4 cm (**Figures 5m** and S14,

Supporting Information). The evaporation rates decreased with surface area. This trend is consistent with previous reports.^[34] Notably, our FePS₃/CNDs 2D/0D nano-heterojunction-based evaporators exhibited a significantly higher water evaporation rate under 1 sun irradiation compared to other 2D photothermal materials such as graphene,^[35] transition metal oxides (TMOs),^[36] transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs),^[37,38] BP,^[39,40] MXenes,^[41–43] etc. (Table S1). This highlights the advantage of MPC₃-based nano-heterojunctions for photothermal water evaporation applications.

As a complement, we conducted detailed investigations of solar desalination performance. We found a significant reduction in Na⁺, Mg²⁺, and Ca²⁺ with concentrations well below the World Health Organization (WHO) standards (**Figure 5n**).^[44]

Based on our experiments, the mechanism behind the high water evaporation rates of FePS₃/CNDs nano-heterojunctions-based converters is as follows (Figure S15, Supporting Information): Upon photoexcitation, incident photons are efficiently absorbed by the FePS₃/CNDs nano-heterojunction. What results is an excitation of electrons from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB). When CNDs are present, the light absorption, especially in the UV-

vis range, is enhanced. At the forefront are π - π^* electronic transitions and surface state-mediated absorption processes.

Subsequently, these excited carriers undergo non-radiative relaxation. Excess energy is, hereby, released in the form of heat and the system temperature increases. After relaxation, a low-energy trap state at the nano-heterojunction between FePS₃ and CNDs is populated. At the trap state, photogenerated carriers across the FePS₃/CNDs nano-heterojunction are confined. This way, radiative recombination pathways are inhibited within the CNDs and non-radiative processes are active. All trapped carriers ultimately recombine through non-radiative pathways and release additional thermal energy that contributes to the overall photothermal conversion. Moreover, trapping electrons at nanoscale dimensions is likely to promote localized heating.^[45] This localized heating effect not only enhances the solar-driven interfacial evaporation of water molecules, but also minimizes heat dissipation losses.

Conclusion

In this work, FePS₃ nanosheets were employed as templates for the synthesis of FePS₃/CNDs 2D/0D nano-heterojunctions with varying compositions, which were subsequently utilized as photothermal

materials for efficient interfacial solar evaporation. The formation of the nano-heterojunctions was confirmed by TEM and PL spectroscopy. Absorption spectroscopy, FDTD simulations, fs-TAS, and PL investigations corroborated that the introduction of CNDs endows the nano-heterojunction with significantly enhanced local heating, improved light absorption, effective charge carrier trapping, and optimized non-radiative transition pathways. Photothermal conversion and water evaporation experiments validated the success of our design, with FeCx@S achieving an evaporation rate exceeding $1.68 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ that surpasses the theoretical limit of typical 2D evaporators under 1 Sun irradiation ($\approx 1.47 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) and that outperforms most reported 2D material-based evaporators. This work expands the potential of MPCh₃ materials upon hybridization with 0D nanostructures, thereby enhancing the functional complexity, and it provides unprecedented insights into the development of high-performance photothermal materials.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] H. Yu, H. Jin, M. Qiu, Y. Liang, P. Sun, C. Cheng, P. Wu, Y. Wang, X. Wu, D. Chu, M. Zheng, T. Qiu, Y. Lu, B. Zhang, W. Mai, X. Yang, G. Owens, H. Xu, *Advanced Materials* **2024**, *36*, 2414045.
- [2] Y. Zhang, Y. Wang, B. Yu, K. Yin, Z. Zhang, *Advanced Materials* **2022**, *34*, 2200108.
- [3] B. Yang, Z. Zhang, P. Liu, X. Fu, J. Wang, Y. Cao, R. Tang, X. Du, W. Chen, S. Li, H. Yan, Z. Li, X. Zhao, G. Qin, X.-Q. Chen, L. Zuo, *Nature* **2023**, *622*, 499.

- [4] H. Zou, X. Meng, X. Zhao, J. Qiu, *Advanced Materials* **2023**, *35*, 2207262.
- [5] C. Dang, Y. Cao, H. Nie, W. Lang, J. Zhang, G. Xu, M. Zhu, *Nat Water* **2024**, *2*, 115.
- [6] M. S. Irshad, N. Arshad, M. S. Asghar, Y. Hao, M. Alomar, S. Zhang, J. Zhang, J. Guo, I. Ahmed, N. Mushtaq, M. A. K. Y. Shah, L. Noureen, S. Wageh, O. A. Al-Hartomy, A. Kalam, V.-D. Dao, H. Wang, X. Wang, H. Zhang, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2023**, *33*, 2304936.
- [7] Y. Wang, T. Guo, Z. Tian, K. Bibi, Y.-Z. Zhang, H. N. Alshareef, *Advanced Materials* **2022**, *34*, 2108560.
- [8] D. Yuan, Y. Dou, Z. Wu, Y. Tian, K.-H. Ye, Z. Lin, S. X. Dou, S. Zhang, *Chem. Rev.* **2022**, *122*, 957.
- [9] X. Cui, Q. Ruan, X. Zhuo, X. Xia, J. Hu, R. Fu, Y. Li, J. Wang, H. Xu, *Chem. Rev.* **2023**, *123*, 6891.
- [10] M. Barua, M. Monis Ayyub, P. Vishnoi, K. Pramoda, C. N. R. Rao, *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **2019**, *7*, 22500.
- [11] Q. Fu, L. W. Wong, F. Zheng, X. Zheng, C. S. Tsang, K. H. Lai, W. Shen, T. H. Ly, Q. Deng, J. Zhao, *Nat Commun* **2023**, *14*, 6462.
- [12] L. Chen, J.-T. Ren, Z.-Y. Yuan, *Green Chem.* **2022**, *24*, 713.
- [13] H. Wang, P. Cheng, B. Wu, Y. Yan, P. Schaaf, Z. Sofer, D.

- Wang, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2024**, *34*, 2407432.
- [14] R. Gusmão, Z. Sofer, M. Pumera, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58*, 9326.
- [15] H. Wang, Y. Bo, M. Klingenhof, J. Peng, D. Wang, B. Wu, J. Pezoldt, P. Cheng, A. Knauer, W. Hua, H. Wang, P. A. van Aken, Z. Sofer, P. Strasser, D. M. Guldi, P. Schaaf, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2024**, *34*, 2310942.
- [16] Z. Xie, Y. Duo, Z. Lin, T. Fan, C. Xing, L. Yu, R. Wang, M. Qiu, Y. Zhang, Y. Zhao, X. Yan, H. Zhang, *Advanced Science* **2020**, *7*, 1902236.
- [17] O. Z. Sharaf, N. Rizk, C. J. Munro, C. P. Joshi, W. Waheed, E. Abu-Nada, A. Alazzam, M. N. Martin, *Energy Conversion and Management* **2021**, *244*, 114463.
- [18] D. Xu, Z. Li, L. Li, J. Wang, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2020**, *30*, 2000712.
- [19] T. Liu, J. Ding, Z. Su, G. Wei, *Materials Today Energy* **2017**, *6*, 79.
- [20] J. Azadmanjiri, P. Kumar, V. K. Srivastava, Z. Sofer, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* **2020**, *3*, 3116.
- [21] A. Taranova, E. Moretti, K. Akbar, G. Dastgeer, A. Vomiero, *Nano Energy* **2024**, *128*, 109872.
- [22] H. Wang, Y. Jiao, B. Wu, D. Wang, Y. Hu, F. Liang, C. Shen,

- A. Knauer, D. Ren, H. Wang, P. A. van Aken, H. Zhang, Z. Sofer, M. Grätzel, P. Schaaf, *Angewandte Chemie n.d.*, *n/a*, e202217253.
- [23] S. Xue, L. Chen, Z. Liu, H.-M. Cheng, W. Ren, *ACS Nano* **2018**, *12*, 5297.
- [24] X. Li, D. Fan, C. Zhao, X. Yang, *Surfaces and Interfaces* **2024**, *51*, 104732.
- [25] Y. Jin, M. Yan, Y. Jin, K. Li, Y. Dedkov, E. Voloshina, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2022**, *126*, 16061.
- [26] Z. Cheng, T. A. Shifa, F. Wang, Y. Gao, P. He, K. Zhang, C. Jiang, Q. Liu, J. He, *Advanced Materials* **2018**, *30*, 1707433.
- [27] F. Kargar, E. A. Coleman, S. Ghosh, J. Lee, M. J. Gomez, Y. Liu, A. S. Magana, Z. Barani, A. Mohammadzadeh, B. Debnath, R. B. Wilson, R. K. Lake, A. A. Balandin, *ACS Nano* **2020**, *14*, 2424.
- [28] B. Geng, H. Qin, F. Zheng, W. Shen, P. Li, K. Wu, X. Wang, X. Li, D. Pan, L. Shen, *Nanoscale* **2019**, *11*, 7209.
- [29] P. Cheng, H. Wang, H. Wang, P. A. van Aken, D. Wang, P. Schaaf, *Advanced Energy and Sustainability Research* **2021**, *2*, 2000083.
- [30] P. Cheng, Y. An, A. K.-Y. Jen, D. Lei, *Advanced Materials* **2024**, *36*, 2309459.

- [31] P. Cheng, D. Wang, P. Schaaf, *Advanced Sustainable Systems* **2022**, 6, 2200115.
- [32] P. Cheng, M. Klingenhof, H. Honig, L. Zhang, P. Strasser, P. Schaaf, D. Lei, D. Wang, *Advanced Materials* **2025**, 37, 2415655.
- [33] J. Wang, Y. Li, L. Deng, N. Wei, Y. Weng, S. Dong, D. Qi, J. Qiu, X. Chen, T. Wu, *Advanced Materials* **2017**, 29, 1603730.
- [34] T. Gao, Y. Wang, X. Wu, P. Wu, X. Yang, Q. Li, Z. Zhang, D. Zhang, G. Owens, H. Xu, *Science Bulletin* **2022**, 67, 1572.
- [35] B. Huo, D. Jiang, X. Cao, H. Liang, Z. Liu, C. Li, J. Liu, *Carbon* **2019**, 142, 13.
- [36] X. Ming, A. Guo, G. Wang, X. Wang, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* **2018**, 185, 333.
- [37] X. Yang, Y. Yang, L. Fu, M. Zou, Z. Li, A. Cao, Q. Yuan, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2018**, 28, 1704505.
- [38] Q. Wang, F. Jia, A. Huang, Y. Qin, S. Song, Y. Li, M. A. C. Arroyo, *Desalination* **2020**, 481, 114359.
- [39] M. Li, Q. Zhao, S. Zhang, D. Li, H. Li, X. Zhang, B. Xing, *Environ. Sci.: Nano* **2020**, 7, 414.
- [40] Z. Li, W. Cai, X. Wang, Y. Hu, Z. Gui, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2021**, 582, 496.
- [41] K. Li, T.-H. Chang, Z. Li, H. Yang, F. Fu, T. Li, J. S. Ho, P.-Y. Chen, *Advanced Energy Materials* **2019**, 9, 1901687.

- [42] H. Zhang, X. Shen, E. Kim, M. Wang, J.-H. Lee, H. Chen, G. Zhang, J.-K. Kim, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2022**, *32*, 2111794.
- [43] B. Zhang, Q. Gu, C. Wang, Q. Gao, J. Guo, P. W. Wong, C. T. Liu, A. K. An, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2021**, *13*, 3762.
- [44] P. Cheng, M. Ziegler, V. Ripka, H. Wang, K. Pollok, F. Langenhorst, D. Wang, P. Schaaf, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2022**, *14*, 16894.
- [45] A. Allahbakhsh, Z. Jarrahi, G. Farzi, A. Shavandi, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2023**, *467*, 143472.

Supporting Information

Enhanced Photothermal Conversion through 2D/0D Nano-Heterojunction Engineering for Highly Efficient Solar Desalination

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Experimental Procedures

Chemicals. Red phosphorus (99.999%) and sulfur (99.999%) were purchased from STREM, Germany. Isopropanol (IPA) (99%), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), 1,3,6-trinitropyrene (TNP) and branched polyethylenimine (BPEI₁₈₀₀) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Deionized water (18.2 MΩ•cm) was purchased from Purelab Ultra. Carbon dioxide (CO₂, 99.998%) and helium (He, 99.9999%) were purchased from Carbagas Company.

Characterization. The morphology of the prepared FePS₃ nanosheets was characterized using atomic force microscopy (AFM) equipped with a Bruker Dimension Icon setup operating in air. The tip model is TESPA-V2, and the tip stiffness K is 42 N m⁻¹. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) samples were prepared by the drop-casting method: a drop of sample dispersion was placed on a carbon-coated Cu grid and dried in air. Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) studies were performed using a spherical aberration-corrected microscope (JEOL JEM-ARM 200F) with a DCOR probe corrector (CEOS GmbH) at 200 kV. High-angle annular dark field (HAADF)-STEM imaging was performed with a convergent semi-angle of 20.4 mrad and a collection semi-angle of 70-300 mrad. Electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS) measurements were performed with a Gatan K2 Summit camera at a collection semi-angle of 111 mrad. EELS spectrum imaging was performed with a dispersion of 0.25 eV/channel using a 4000 x 4000-pixel wide detector for simultaneous acquisition of elemental spectral images. The raw spectrum image data were first denoised using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with the Multivariate Statistical Analysis (MSA) plug-in (HREM Research Inc.) in Gatan DigitalMicrograph and then smoothed using its spatial filter.

The Raman studies of the films were performed on a WITec CRM200 confocal Raman microscopy system with a laser excitation energy of 532 nm and an air-cooled charge-coupled device (CCD) as the detector. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were recorded with a FEI Quanta FEG 250 instrument S3 (FEI corporate, Hillsboro, Oregon, USA). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy measurements were carried out with a Thermo Scientific K-Alpha X-ray photoelectron spectrometer with a basic chamber pressure of $\approx 10^{-9}$ mbar and an Al anode as the X-ray source (X-ray radiation of 1486 eV). Spot sizes of 400 μm and pass energies of 200.00 eV for wide energy scans and 10.00-20.00 eV for scans were used. All XPS spectra were calibrated using the C 1s peak at 284.8 eV as a reference. X-ray diffraction (XRD, Bruker D8 X-ray diffractometer) was used to measure the crystal structure of the samples. UV-Vis absorption spectra were measured using a Cary 5000 instrument.

Femtosecond transient absorption spectra (fs-TAS) were acquired with the HELIOS (0 to 7900 ps) from Ultrafast Systems using transient absorption pump/probe detection systems. The white light of the probe beam was generated by focusing a fraction of the 1050 Hz Ti:sapphire output (Clark-MXR, CPA-2101, 775 nm fundamental, 150 fs pulse width) onto a 2 mm (fs-TAS, vis) or 1 cm (fs-TAS, NIR) sapphire disk. The 387 nm excitation

wavelength was generated by second harmonic generation (SHG) of the 775nm laser output. Samples were prepared in 2 × 10 mm optical glass cuvettes and purged with argon for 20 min. The HELIOS measurements were performed under ambient conditions with continuous stirring.

Synthesis of bulk FePS₃. A stoichiometric mixture of iron, phosphorus, and sulfur, equivalent to 15 g of thiophosphite, was loaded into a quartz glass ampoule (30 × 150 mm², wall thickness: 3 mm) and hermetically sealed under high vacuum (<1×10⁻³ Pa) using an oxygen/hydrogen welding torch. The sealed ampoule was then placed in a muffle furnace, where the FePS₃ precursor underwent thermal treatment at 650 °C for 120 h, followed by an additional 120 h at 700 °C. The heating and cooling rates were both controlled at 1 °C/min.

Preparation of carbon nanodots (CNDs). CNDs were synthesized via a hydrothermal method using TNP and BPEI as precursors. Specifically, 0.1 g of TNP and a designated amount of BPEI were dispersed in 40 mL of deionized water with the aid of ultrasonication. The resulting solution was then transferred into a 100 mL poly(tetrafluoroethylene)-lined autoclave. The BPEI content was varied from 0.4 to 1.6 g, and its molecular weight ranged from 600 to 10,000, while the TNP quantity remained constant at 0.1 g. The hydrothermal reaction was carried out at 200 °C for 12 h in an oven, yielding a crude aqueous CNDs dispersions. To eliminate unreacted precursors, the synthesized CNDs underwent purification via filtration and dialysis. Ultimately, a black aqueous CNDs solution was obtained.

Preparation of FePS₃ nanosheets. A mixture of 0.5 g FePS₃ powder and 1.5 mL IPA was placed in a mortar and manually ground for 30 min. Upon evaporation of the grinding solvent, an additional 1.5 mL of IPA was introduced. The resulting ground sample (100 mg) was subsequently dispersed in a 10 mL mixed solvent of IPA and water (1:1 volume ratio) and subjected to ultrasonic treatment in a bath sonicator (sonication frequency ~90 kHz) for 2.0 h. Following sonication, the dispersions were centrifuged at 250 g (Thermo Megafuge 16) for 30 min. After centrifugation, the upper 3/4 portion of the supernatant was collected and underwent a second centrifugation under identical conditions. Finally, the top 2/3 fraction of the resulting supernatant was extracted for further characterization.

Preparation of FePS₃/CNDs nano-heterojunction based evaporators. A 5 wt% aqueous solution of PVA was prepared by dissolving PVA completely through heating at 80 °C for 60 min. Nano-heterojunction dispersions were obtained by blending 10 mL of FePS₃ nanosheet dispersion with CNDs dispersion at volume ratios of 10:1, 10:2, and 10:4, followed by the addition of 1 mL of PVA aqueous solution to each mixture, resulting in FeC1, FeC2, and FeC4, respectively. The prepared dispersions were uniformly drop-cast onto blank sponges and subsequently dried in an oven at 110 °C for 20 min. This drop-casting process was repeated until the dispersion was fully utilized, leading to the formation of FePS₃/CNDs nano-heterojunction-based evaporators with different compositions. Additionally, 10 mL of FePS₃ nanosheet dispersion and 1 mL of CNDs dispersion were

each separately combined with 1 mL of PVA aqueous solution, and the resulting mixtures were drop-cast onto blank sponges following the same procedure, yielding FePS₃@S and CNDs@S evaporators.

Water evaporation experiments. A light evaporator with dimensions of 2 × 2 × 0.5 cm³ was utilized for water evaporation experiments under 100 mW cm⁻² (AM 1.5G) illumination. The mass loss due to evaporation was determined by measuring the weight difference before and after the process using an analytical balance (KERN, 0.1 mg accuracy), which was subsequently used to calculate the evaporation rate and assess water evaporation efficiency. An infrared (IR) camera was employed to capture real-time surface temperature variations throughout the evaporation process. The condensed water was collected and analyzed using inductively coupled plasma - optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, Varian ICP-OES 715ES).

Finite difference time domain (FDTD) Simulation. The reflectance and electric field enhancement (EFE) simulations were performed using the FDTD method implemented in the Lumerical FDTD Solutions software. A simplified periodic unit cell model representing the FePS₃/CNDs nano-heterojunction structure was established for simulation. The dimensions of the nano-heterojunction were set to 160 nm × 160 nm × 10 nm. Periodic boundary conditions were applied along the x- and y-directions, while a perfectly matched layer was introduced in the z-direction to separate the CNDs substrate from the FePS₃ nanosheets. For both reflectance and EFE simulations, the nano-heterojunction was illuminated using a total-field scattered-field source with incident wavelengths ranging from 300 to 2500 nm.

Figures

Figure S1. High-resolution XPS of a) Fe 2p, b) P 2p, and c) S 2p spectral regions of FePS₃ nanosheets on Si substrate.

Figure S2. Raman spectrum of bulk FePS₃ nanosheets.

Figure S3. EELS spectra of a) P and S, c) Fe of FePS₃ nanosheets.

Figure S4. AFM images of a) FeC1 and the b) corresponding height profiles.

Figure S5. The emission spectra of a) CNDs and b) FeC1 in IPA/ water at different wavelengths of photoexcitation.

Figure S6. Differential absorption spectra at various time delays of fs-TAS raw data for a) FePS₃ and b) FeC1 obtained from pump-probe experiments after photoexcitation at 390 nm.

Figure S7. Relative populations of the fitted species of a) FePS₃ and b) FeC1. The corresponding evolution-associated spectra (EAS) of the deconvoluted species are shown in Figures 4 b and d, respectively.

Figure S8. Electric field enhancement distribution for a) FeC2, and b) FeC4.

Figure S9. Constructed FDTD models for a) FePS₃ nanosheets, b) FeC1, c) FeC2 and d) FeC4.

Figure S10. The photo shows the ultralight nature of the FeC1@S.

Figure S11. Water contact angle measurements of FeC1@S.

Figure S12. (a) Reflection of the blank@S, CNDs@S, FePS₃@S and FeC1@S from wavelength 300 to 2500 nm. (b) AM 1.5G solar spectrum.

Figure S13. Real-time measurement of the surface temperatures of the blank sponge and FeC1@S as monitored by an IR camera during photothermal water evaporation under 1 sun irradiation for 35 min.

Figure S14. The photographs of evaporators with side lengths of 2, 3, and 4 cm, respectively.

Figure S15. Schematic illustration showing the solar-thermal conversion process from FePS₃/CNDs nano-heterojunctions.

Table

Table S1. The photothermal performance of 2D materials based samples under 1 sun illumination

Materials ^a	Evaporation rate (kg m ⁻² h ⁻¹)	Design	References
WO _x	≈1.10	2D	[1]
MoS ₂ -SWNT	≈1.00	2D	[2]
MoS ₂	1.20	2D	[3]
BP	1.63	2D	[4]
BP	≈0.96	2D	[5]
N-doped graphene /carbon	≈1.56	3D	[6]
rGO/polypyrrole	1.44	2D	[7]
MBene	1.59	2D	[8]
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	1.33	2D	[9]
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	≈1.80	3D	[10]
porphyrin/Ti ₃ C ₂ -MXene	1.14	2D	[11]
NiPS ₃	1.48	3D	[12]
FePS ₃ /CNDs (10:1)	1.68	3D	This Work

^a SWNT is a single-walled nanotube; BP is black phosphorus; rGO is graphene oxide; MBene is transition metal boride.

References

- [1] X. Ming, A. Guo, G. Wang, X. Wang, *Sol. Energ. Mater. Sol. C.* 2018, 185, 333–341.
- [2] X. Yang, Y. Yang, L. Fu, M. Zou, Z. Li, A. Cao, Q. Yuan, *Adv. Funct. Mater.s* 2018, 28, 1704505.
- [3] Q. Wang, F. Jia, A. Huang, Y. Qin, S. Song, Y. Li, M. A. C. Arroyo, *Desalination* 2020, 481, 114359.
- [4] M. Li, Q. Zhao, S. Zhang, D. Li, H. Li, X. Zhang, B. Xing, *Environ. Sci.: Nano* 2020, 7, 414–423.
- [5] Z. Li, W. Cai, X. Wang, Y. Hu, Z. Gui, *J. Colloid Interf. Sci.* 2021, 582, 496–505.
- [6] B. Huo, D. Jiang, X. Cao, H. Liang, Z. Liu, C. Li, J. Liu, *Carbon* 2019, 142, 13-19.
- [7] M. Zhang, F. Xu, W. Liu, Y. Hou, L. Su, X.Zhang, R. Zhang, L. Zhou, X. Yan, M. Wang, X. Hou, Y. Cao, *Nano Research*, 2023, 16, 4219-4224.
- [8] M. Chang, L. Ai, R. Yang, X.Wang, Y. Xu, J. Jiang, *Chem. Eng. J.* 2024, 486, 150078.
- [9] K. Li, T.-H. Chang, Z. Li, H. Yang, F. Fu, T. Li, J. S. Ho, P.-Y. Chen, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 2019, 9, 1901687.
- [10] H. Zhang, X. Shen, E. Kim, M. Wang, J.-H. Lee, H. Chen, G. Zhang, J.-K. Kim, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2022, 32, 2111794.
- [11] B. Zhang, Q. Gu, C. Wang, Q. Gao, J. Guo, P.W. Wong, C.T. Liu, A.K. An, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2021, 13, 3762-3770.
- [12] H. Wang, Y. Bo, M. Klingenhof, J. Peng, D. Wang, B.Wu, J. Pezoldt, P. Cheng, A. Knauer, W. Hua, H. Wang, P. A. van Aken, Z. Sofer, P. Strasser, D. M. Guldi, P. Schaaf, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2024, 34, 2310942.